

Exploring Surface Plasmon Polaritons and Light at Interfaces (Rev. 1)

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Abstract: Vision relies on light, which enables the perception of the world around us. Modern advancements have transformed how we generate, control, and detect light, from incandescent bulbs to lasers and photodetectors. These innovations go beyond human vision, powering technologies like optical communications and data storage. Optical fibres, offering high bandwidth and low energy loss, now carry most telecommunications signals. The integration of optics and electronics, especially at the nanoscale, holds the potential for enhanced speed and efficiency in computing. Nano-optics, focusing on confined light fields, boosts the efficiency of light sources such as LEDs and lasers. Nanoscale waveguides and the manipulation of slow light are critical steps toward the future of optical communication and quantum information processing.

Keywords: Surface Plasmon Polaritons (SPPs), Nano-optics, Light manipulation, Optical communication, Nanoscale waveguides, Photonic mode density, Confined optical fields, Slow light, Optical fibers, Quantum information processing

Chapter 1: General Introduction

Human vision, in essence, is a natural process to which light plays an important role. Three steps are involved in the simple process of vision: the light is emitted from a source, it gets scattered by an object, and it gets detected upon interaction with the eye. Technology has developed all three aspects. Starting from the incandescent bulb to the fluorescent tube and LEDs, efficiency and directionality of emission have vastly improved. Since the invention of lasers, there has been great recognition that their work revolutionized optical communications, storage, and micromachining. Today, detectors vary from compact solid-state photodetectors to single-photon counters while materials can be engineered so as to scatter, absorb, or transmit light over nearly any frequency range. Consequently, light has been put into use far beyond its conventional purpose of vision.

Today, most telecommunication signals are carried by optical fibres due to their wide bandwidth and low power loss relative to electrical cables. At the nodes in the communications network, electronic amplifiers, interconnects and computers handle these signals, but could be faster and more powerful if they employed optics as well. The demand for effective integration of optics and electronics has driven the recent, rapid expansion of nano-optics.

Nano-optics concern the science and application of light confined to nanoscale dimensions, usually tens to hundreds of nanometers. The light sources placed in confined optical fields will radiate more effectively than in open space since there is a higher photonic mode density within confined environments. This will enhance their performance in LEDs and lasers. Efficiency and emission directionality are both enhanced when emission is directed into a nanoscale waveguide mode. This is particularly of great worth in chip-based sources of non-classical light, which will be very important in integrated quantum information systems. Development of waveguides with small mode volumes on a nanometer scale marks an important step toward nano-optics use in optical computing and communication.

1.1 Overcoming the Diffraction Limit with Surface Plasmon Polaritons

The diffraction limit is the traditional smallest size to which light can be concentrated, using standard optical elements. The limit was first derived by Ernst Abbe in 1873 [8]. According to Abbe, the smallest size Δx to which light can be focused in one dimension is on the order of

$$\Delta x \approx \frac{2\pi}{\Delta k_x} = \frac{\lambda_0}{2}, \quad (1.1)$$

where Δk_x is the maximum possible spread of the wavevector component k_x and λ_0 is the wavelength in free space.

Recently, scientists have learned that light can be confined to a smaller scale than in free space by utilizing surface plasmon polaritons (SPPs) [9]. Surface plasmon polaritons are propagating solutions of Maxwell's equations at an interface between a dielectric and a metal. They are electromagnetic waves coupled to oscillations of free electrons on the surface of the metal. The fact that SPPs are confined to the interface has caused much excitement [3, 10, 11], because of possible applications involving light control on the nanometer scale.

1.1.1 Surface plasmon polaritons on a flat interface

For a metal-dielectric interface normal to the spatial direction $\hat{z}$, the dispersion of an SPP propagating in the $\hat{x}$ direction is [9]

$$k_x = k_0 \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_d \epsilon_m}{\epsilon_d + \epsilon_m}}. \quad (1.2)$$

Here $k_0 = \omega/c$ is the wavevector in free space, ϵ_m and ϵ_d are the dielectric constants of the metal and dielectric, respectively. When $\epsilon_m < -\epsilon_d$, $k_x > k_0$. The wavevector in free space is

$$\epsilon k_0^2 = k_x^2 + k_z^2, \quad (1.3)$$

where k_z is the wavevector in the direction normal to the surface. As a result, when $k_x > k_0$, the wavevector normal to the interface is imaginary and the electromagnetic field decays exponentially in that direction. A sketch of the z -dependence of the magnitude of the H_y component of the SPP field is depicted in figure

1.1. The field peaks on the surface and decays exponentially in both media. For the case of an interface between Au and air, and a free-space wavelength of $1.5 \mu\text{m}$, the decay length is on the order of one micrometer into air and 10 nm into Au. The confinement is thus only slightly smaller than the wavelength in free space. Higher confinement can be achieved by using a dielectric with a higher permittivity.

The primary cause of propagation losses for surface plasmon polaritons (SPPs) on a gold (Au) surface is heat transfer to the electron bath, commonly referred to as Ohmic losses. When losses are present, the wavevector (k_x) becomes a complex number, which defines a characteristic propagation length (L_{SPP}) . This propagation length represents the distance over which the intensity of the SPP decays to $(1/e)$ of its initial value. For an Au/air interface at a wavelength of $1.5 \mu\text{m}$, this length is typically around $100 \mu\text{m}$. The imaginary part of the wavevector, (k_x'') , increases with $(\epsilon_d^{3/2})$, indicating that Ohmic damping is more pronounced for plasmons at a metal/high-index dielectric interface.

1.1.2 Field directions for surface plasmon polaritons

Surface plasmon polaritons are transverse magnetic (TM) waves. This means that there is no magnetic field in the propagation direction. In the

Figure 1.1: A sketch of a surface plasmon polariton at an interface between a metal and a dielectric. The grey area indicates the metal half-space. The orange area indicates the dielectric. The red line on the left is a representation of the amplitude of the magnetic field of the SPP. The magnetic field peaks on the interface and decays exponentially in both half-spaces. Electric field lines of the SPP are shown on the right.

Picture of figure 1.1, the wave propagates to the right (in the x direction) and the magnetic field oscillates out of the paper plane (in the y direction). The electric field lines point as shown on the right side of the image. Hence, the electric field points primarily out of plane (in the z direction), but also has a longitudinal component (in the direction of propagation, x).

1.1.3 Coupling to surface plasmon polaritons

The fact that $k_x > k_0$ allows SPPs to be focused to sizes smaller than the wavelength in free space is a challenge to couple light from free space to SPPs. The most common approaches for exciting SPPs: Attenuated total reflection (ATR), Using subwavelength scatterer and grating coupling.

ATR employs a dielectric prism of permittivity greater than that of (ϵ_d). Light is totally internally reflected along one side of the prism, and then SPPs can be excited, through evanescent field tunneling, if a metal surface is brought within proximity of the prism. Since light within the prism has a larger wave-vector than in air, it may be phase-matched to the SPPs. This configuration is called Otto configuration. In Kretschmann-Raether configuration, SPPs are excited on a metal film which coated onto the prism. In both the configurations, the coupling efficiency to SPPs is strongly dependent on the angle of incidence and highly selective to the wavelength of light.

A subwavelength scatterer, such as a hole, can provide the additional momentum needed to couple light to SPPs. Provided by the scattering event itself, where the required momentum is supplied. For example, if a single hole is made in a gold film and illuminated with a linearly polarized laser beam, then at its edges the electric field would be most strongly in the direction of the polarization of the beam, which makes the edges reradiate into SPPs with the highest intensity along the direction of the polarization. The result is an intensity that varies as $(\cos^2 \theta)$ where (θ) is the angle relative to the polarization of the laser. This technique has a very wide frequency range but is relatively inefficient.

1.1.4 Surface Plasmon Polariton Waveguide Structures

The spatial extent of SPPs in a direction orthogonal to the direction of propagation can be reduced by coupling two SPPs. For example, if two metal surfaces are brought in the vicinity of each other, the two surface modes can couple to form a waveguide mode. This can occur in two configurations, which are sketched in figure 1.3. Figure 1.3a depicts an insulator-metal-insulator (IMI) configuration, in which a thin layer of metal is surrounded

Figure 1.2: Launching SPPs from a single hole in a gold film. (a) The yellow region indicates gold. The white circle represents a hole in the film. A laser beam is incident with linear polarization in the direction of E . The arrows on the edges of the hole represent the induced electric field. The direction of the arrows is given by boundary conditions at the edges. The length of the arrows represents the magnitude, resulting from a projection of E onto the direction of the arrow. A hole which is significantly smaller than the wavelength can be represented by a dipole emitter. (b) The radiation pattern of a subwavelength hole in a gold film

by two half-spaces of dielectric. The 2D half-spaces are infinite in the direction orthogonal to the paper plane. The two surface plasmon modes couple to form an IMI mode [15, 16, 17], which is confined to the metal slab. In reality, two modes are formed, however only the mode with a symmetric charge distribution is confined to the metal [18]. This mode stays confined for arbitrarily small non-zero metal thickness. If, instead of extending infinitely out of the paper plane, this geometry is placed on a substrate, a 1D waveguide is formed. This waveguide is a metallic nanowire.

We will call the mode having a symmetric charge distribution the "symmetric" mode and modes having an antisymmetric charge distribution "antisymmetric." The electric field lines of the symmetric mode are sketched on the right-hand side of figure 1.3a and on the left we show a sketch of the absolute magnetic field of the SPP. We see from this diagram that this field is strongly concentrated around the wire.

Another possibility is to realize a MIM structure, figure 1.3b. We take two metallic surfaces that are put close to each other with a dielectric in between. In this way, plasmonic modes in the gap are created, as in the previous case. For the symmetric mode there exists a cut off when the width of the waveguide approaches $\pi c / (\sqrt{\epsilon_d} \omega)$. Below this width, only the antisymmetric mode can propagate. The electric and magnetic field lines for the antisymmetric mode are shown in figure 1.3b. Within this configuration, waveguides as narrow as 12 nm have been reported. The spatial extent of the plasmon field is comparable to the width of the waveguide. A one-dimensional analogue of the MIM waveguide is called the slot waveguide. Due to the fact that plasmonic waveguides can confine light down to such a small size, they are in good position to enhance the efficiency of optical emitters. The spatial distribution and symmetry of the mode will have a direct consequence on the efficiency of coupling of an emitter to it.

1.2 Photonic crystal waveguides

Another method of controlling light propagation on small scales utilizes photonic crystal structures. Photonic crystals (PhCs) are periodic arrangements of dielectric materials [21]. The arrangements are carefully engineered to control the dispersion of light in the crystal.

PhCs can be fabricated in one, two or three dimensions. To understand

Figure 1.3: A sketch of magnetic field amplitudes and electric field lines for (a) an IMI waveguide and (b) a MIM waveguide. In both cases, the SPP field is confined to the waveguide.

Figure 1.4: Bragg stack geometry and dispersion. a) Geometry of the Bragg stack. Different colors indicate layers with different refractive indices, n_1 and n_2 . Light is incident from the left, normal to the interfaces. b) A sketch of the dispersion of the Bragg stack. The horizontal axis is wavevector, the vertical axis is frequency. Light of a given frequency must obey the dispersion curve. The solid black lines are allowed modes. At a frequency ω_1 (dark grey dashed line), the wave consists of several Bloch components, indicated by the red dots. At a frequency ω_2 (light grey dashed line), there are no modes due to an avoided crossing between two Bloch modes. The region without modes is called the bandgap.

The basic properties of PhCs, it is instructive to start with the 1D case. In this structure, alternating layers of two dielectrics with a high contrast of refractive index are stacked with period a , as sketched in figure 1.4a. This structure is called a Bragg stack. An optical wave which propagates orthogonal to the layer boundaries is partially reflected at each boundary. For specific wavelengths, the many partial reflections add up constructively to create total reflection. The range of frequencies for which this occurs is called the photonic stop gap [22, 23]. In the photonic stop gap, there are no allowed propagating modes in the structure.

Due to the periodic nature of the structure, light propagating in the crystal obeys Bloch's theorem, similar to electrons in a semiconductor crystal [24]. Bloch's theorem states that the eigenfunctions of the wave equation for a periodic potential are the product of a plane wave e^{iky} and a function $u(y)$ with the periodicity of the crystal lattice. Here k is the wavevector of the plane wave. Consequently, the amplitude of the plane wave is modulated with the periodicity of the structure. As a result, the solution can be expressed as an expansion in m Bloch harmonics. The m -th harmonic has a wave vector $k + mG$, where $G = 2\pi/a$ is the reciprocal lattice vector.

1.2.1 Dispersion in photonic crystal waveguides

Optical properties of a material are conveniently expressed with a dispersion relation, which relates the optical frequency to the wavevector in the material. The dispersion relation for a Bragg stack is depicted in figure 1.4b. Modes which light is allowed to populate are visible as solid black lines. Light of a certain frequency ω_1 , indicated by the dark grey dashed line, excites a forward-propagating mode composed of several Bloch wavevectors, shown as red dots. It also excites a backward-propagating Bloch mode, shown as green dots. For a certain frequency ω_2 , indicated by the light grey dashed line, two Bloch modes would have the same wavevector. Due to reflections at the layer interfaces, these two modes are strongly coupled. The strong coupling causes an avoided crossing in the dispersion diagram, so that a stop gap is created. The stronger the contrast in the refractive indices of the two media, the larger the stop gap [21].

It is easily demonstrated that a stop gap can also be created in two-dimensional structures. Figure 1.5a shows a scanning electron micrograph of a 2D photonic crystal

(PhC), in which a Si-membrane is periodically patterned with airholes, leading to a 2D photonic stop gap. Figure 1.5b plots the relevant band structure as dark grey areas, showing a continuum of states allowed for photons. The range of frequencies between those grey regions is called photonic stop gap.

After removing one line of holes, which means one line defect, a new solution to the wave equation seems apparent in the stop gap. This new solution is related to the mode that exists at the line defect since the missing line of holes now acts as a waveguide for the light. Figures 1.5c and 1.5d show the waveguide with its corresponding dispersion diagram, where the waveguide mode is pointed by a red line. In this waveguide, the light is confined in the waveguide core but its evanescent field extends to the surrounding hole structure.

The mode in the waveguide exhibits very strong dispersion, i.e. the wavevector is highly dependent on the optical frequency. The group velocity of light, v_g , is given by the slope of the dispersion curve:

Figure 1.5: Photonic crystals and their associated dispersion diagrams. a) A scanning electron micrograph (SEM) of a photonic crystal. A periodic arrangement of holes is etched into a Si membrane. b) The dispersion diagram of the PhC. The grey areas indicate a continuum of allowed photonic eigenstates. The white region between the shaded regions is the photonic bandgap. c) An SEM of a PhC waveguide. A row of holes is left missing to create the waveguide. d) The dispersion diagram of the PhC waveguide. The red line indicates the waveguide mode.

Figure 1.6: Mode profiles in a photonic crystal waveguide. Shown is one unit cell of the photonic crystal. The white circles represent air holes in the Si membrane. The waveguide is formed by the missing hole in the middle of the image. a) The electric field intensity for fast light ($v_g = c/15$). The mode is confined to the waveguide core. b) The electric field intensity for slow light ($v_g = c/150$). The mode extends laterally into the crystal lattice. The electric field intensity rises proportionate to the group index. The plots are results of 3-dimensional FDTD simulations, courtesy of T. P. White.

$$v_g \equiv \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial k}. \quad (1.4)$$

At $k = \pi/a$, the slope of the dispersion tends to zero, so that light is slowed down at the corresponding frequencies. The phenomenon of slow light has drawn a lot of attention [7, 25], due to wide-spread applications, ranging from optical delay lines [26], buffers [27], and switches [28, 29], to enhanced nonlinear optics [30]. The point at which the slope of the dispersion curve reaches zero is called the photonic band edge.

1.3 Phase- and polarization-sensitive near-field microscope

One of the key properties of nano-optics is the presence of evanescent waves. In section 1.1.1, we showed that confinement of optical fields beyond the diffraction limit in a given spatial direction can be achieved when the wavevector in that direction exceeds the total wavevector in free space. In that case, for equation 1.3 to still be valid, the wavevector in an orthogonal direction becomes purely imaginary, meaning that the electric field in the orthogonal direction decays exponentially. The ability to confine optical fields beyond the diffraction limit is the basic principle of nano-optics [46]. In this thesis, we consider situations in which there is a wave propagating in one or two spatial directions and exponentially decaying in another.

A near-field microscope works by introducing a subwavelength-sized probe into the evanescent field of the wave. If the probe scatters the field into free space, to be collected by a detector, the microscope is called scattering-type [48]. On the other hand, if the probe contains a small aperture at the end of a fiber through which the field is picked up, the microscope is called collection-type [49]. In this thesis, we use a collection-type near-field microscope.

A scanning-electron micrograph (SEM) of a near-field aperture probe is depicted in figure 1.7a. The probe is made from an optical fiber, which is first heated in the middle with a CO₂ laser while being pulled on both ends. The heating/pulling procedure is continued until the fiber breaks. What remains on each side of the breaking point is a glass tip, with a radius of curvature of ≈ 20 nm. Next, the tip is coated with a layer of aluminum with a thickness of ≈ 150 nm. The final step in probe fabrication is to cut

Figure 1.7: Geometry of the near-field probe and its principle of operation.

a) A scanning-electron micrograph of the probe. The circular glass aperture has a diameter on the order of 150 nm. The aluminum coating has a thickness of 150 nm. The coating prevents light entering the probe at any other position except through the glass aperture. b) The principle of operation of the probe. The grey and yellow areas are materials of different dielectric constants. An optical wave propagates in the x direction and is evanescent in the z direction. The evanescent tail of the wave's electric field (marked in red) polarizes the aperture, as indicated by positive and negative charges in the coating. The aperture re-radiates into propagating modes of the fiber (not shown in the image).

the end of the probe with a focused-ion beam, so that what remains is a circular glass aperture with a diameter on the order of 150 nm, surrounded by the aluminum coating.

The principle of operation of the aperture probe is sketched in figure 1.7b. The grey area indicates a semi-space with dielectric constant different from that of the yellow semi-space. An optical mode propagates at the interface, in the x direction, and is evanescent in the z direction. The x-component of the electric field of a sample is portrayed by the red line. In this illustration, the field peaks at the interface. The probe is brought into the evanescent field of the sample. The probe-sample distance is controlled with a shear-force feedback loop (not shown in the image), and is kept at about 20 nm [50]. The probe needs to be kept as close as possible to the surface, without touching it, for maximum signal and to prevent damage to the probe, respectively. The electric field polarizes the probe aperture, as indicated by positive and negative charges in the figure. The glass core at the apex of the probe is too small to support propagating

Figure 1.8: A schematic of the phase- and polarization-sensitive near-field microscope. A laser beam is incident from the bottom. It is split by a polarizing beam splitter (PBS) into the sample branch and the reference branch. The sample branch excites a wave in the structure. The evanescent tail of the wave is collected by the aperture probe and guided down the probe fiber. The probe fiber is mixed with the reference branch.

fiber modes, however the core expands away from the apex. The near field of the polarized core extends in the z direction to the cutoff point, where propagating modes exist in the fiber. At this point, the near field excites these propagating modes, which carry the signal through the fiber towards a photodetector. For more details, see [51].

A schematic of the phase- and polarization-sensitive near-field microscope is depicted in figure 1.8. A laser beam, shown as a red line, is incident from the bottom. In this thesis we use a continuous-wave laser source (HP/Agilent 8168F), tunable between 1450 nm and 1590 nm. The beam is split by a polarizing beam splitter (PBS) into two branches. One branch goes to the sample and excites the wave which we want to investigate. The near field of the wave is collected with a probe, as described above, and guided by the probe fiber. The other branch of the beam, which we will call the reference branch, does not go to the sample. Instead, it is sent through a pair of acousto-optic modulators (AOMs) and a half-wave plate ($\lambda/2$), labelled with a green “1”, before being mixed in a fiber with the sample branch. The AOMs are modulated at frequencies which differ by $\Delta\omega = 40$ kHz, such that the sample and reference branch beat with that frequency. The beat frequency is fed into a lock-in amplifier to which the photodetectors are connected. In this way, sensitivity of detection is greatly enhanced, in what is termed heterodyne detection [52, 53]. After they have been mixed, the sample and reference branch together go through another half-wave plate, labelled with a green “2”, are split by a second PBS and sent to two different detectors, noted as Ch1 and Ch2. The polarization detection scheme, together with half-wave plate 1, allows for the detection of the orientation of the in-plane electric field vector [54, 51]. For example, if we are studying a plasmonic slot waveguide, we would like to measure in Ch1 the electric field component orthogonal to the waveguide, and in Ch2 the electric field component parallel to the waveguide. These two electric field directions are indicated by the red coordinate system in figure 1.9. The reference beam is linearly polarized, but the direction of polarization makes an arbitrary angle with the red axes. The direction of polarization of the reference beam is indicated by the blue arrow. To detect the electric field parallel to the waveguide and that orthogonal to the waveguide with equal sensitivity, we rotate the polarization direction of the reference branch such that it makes an angle of 45° to the red axes. This is performed by setting the half-waveplate “1”.

Chapter 2: Modal symmetry in plasmonic slot waveguides

In this respect, plasmonic slot waveguides represent highly versatile and submicron-size devices that can easily be fabricated on glass substrates. Moreover, in such waveguides, multiple light-matter interactions become possible, and their characteristics strongly depend on the symmetry of the electric field inside a waveguide. For the purpose of this paper, we performed electric field measurements in waveguides within a wide range of slot widths using a phase and polarization-sensitive near-field microscope. The experiments indeed showed that the field across the slot gap has an antisymmetric pattern, later confirmed by numerical simulations. The calculations also showed that the field is confined within a lateral dimension about 10 times smaller than the free-space wavelength. These findings are important in advancing quantum plasmonics, where the symmetry of the electric field is a critical factor.

2.1 Introduction

Strong electric fields can be achieved by coupling the SPP modes of two parallel metal surfaces in an MIM waveguide. In contrast to purely dielectric optical waveguides, in which some evanescent field inevitably extends into the surrounding material [55], most of the electric field in an MIM waveguide is confined to the core, even for arbitrarily narrow spacings between the two metal surfaces. Similar confinement exists also in triangular channel guides [56] and a slot in a metal film, in which SPPs on the sides of the slot couple to form a guided mode that is confined to the core in two dimensions [57, 58, 59, 60, 61]. The ability to access the waveguide from the air side and introduce materials or particles into the gap opens up many potential applications. The strong field enhancement between two metal surfaces can be used to sense the presence of molecules [62], or to produce nonlinear effects [63, 64, 65, 66]. The associated small mode volume could be useful for coupling the emission of individual quantum emitters introduced into the gap to guided modes, which may lead to a nanoscopic source of light on a chip [67].

When considering any near-field interaction between matter and waveguide modes, the distribution and symmetry of the field must be carefully studied. In this Chapter we report near-field measurements of the spatial symmetry of the electric field in a plasmonic slot waveguide. We show that there is only one mode in waveguides of height and width considered in this work. The field of this mode is such that it sets up opposite charges across the gap, i.e. the mode is antisymmetric [68]. Numerical calculations confirm this symmetry and indicate subwavelength confinement of the mode. Although there have been several far-field input/output studies of plasmonic slot waveguides at optical frequencies [59, 69, 70, 71, 72], none of those provide direct information about the symmetry of the mode.

2.2 Experiments

2.2.1 Experimental details

Slots are fabricated by focused ion beam (FEI Helios) milling in a layer of gold, which was evaporated by physical vapour deposition on a BK7 glass substrate. The thickness of the gold film is 80 ± 5 nm. Slot widths w range from 40 nm to 120 nm, with a fixed length of 17 μm . The slot width and

Figure 2.1: A diagram of the structure. The thickness t of the gold film is 80 ± 5 nm. The length l of the slots is $17 \mu\text{m}$. The width w of the slots ranged from 40 nm to 120 nm.

length were measured with a scanning electron microscope. A diagram of the sample is shown in figure 2.1 Continuous wave laser light from a commercial telecom laser is focused to a spot with a diameter of $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ ($1/e$ in amplitude). The light impinges through the glass substrate, perpendicular to the gold layer. The free-space wavelength used in the experiment is $1.55 \mu\text{m}$. At this wavelength, the dielectric constant of gold was experimentally determined by ellipsometry to have a value of $-115.67+11.34i$, and the dielectric constant of the substrate is 2.25. The light is linearly polarized orthogonal to the long axis of the slot. A phase- and polarization-sensitive near-field microscope [52, 54] is used to image the electric field from the air side of the gold film.

2.2.2 Measurement results

Figure 2.2 shows the measured amplitude and phase of the electric field component orthogonal to the long axis of the slot. The slot extends from the top left to the bottom right corner of the image, making an angle of ~ 15 degrees with the x-axis. The amplitude, figure 2.2(a), above the slot peaks in the middle of the slot, corresponding to the excitation beam. A modulation is superimposed on the amplitude, with a measured period of $1.0 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$. The phase image, figure 2.2(b), shows a similar distribution

Figure 2.2: The measured near-field amplitude (a) and phase (b) of the electric field component orthogonal to the long axis of the slot, as indicated by the white arrow. The slot makes an angle of ~ 15 degrees with the x -axis. The amplitude follows the excitation beam profile, with a superimposed modulation. The modulation period is $1.0 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$.

as the amplitude image in the slot area. The wavefronts parallel to the slot are waves with a wavelength of $\sim 1.5 \mu\text{m}$, propagating to the top and bottom of the image. These are surface plasmon polaritons excited at the slot, propagating on the smooth gold/air interface.

When the component of the electric field parallel to the slot waveguide is measured (figure 2.3), only a modulation is observed. The field exhibits a node along the center of the slot. The modulation period of $0.5 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$, best observed close to the slot ends, is twice as fast as the one observed for the perpendicular field direction (figure 2.2(a)). The phase in figure 2.3(b) and (c) varies with a period of $1.0 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$. The two opposite metal edges of the slot are found to be in anti-phase. This indicates that the wave which gives rise to the observed pattern along the slot sets up opposite charges across the slot gap.

Figure 2.3: The measured near-field amplitude (a) and phase (b) of the electric field component parallel to the long axis of the slot, as indicated by the white arrow. A closeup of the part of the phase image which is surrounded by a dashed white rectangle is shown in (c). The field is antisymmetric, with opposite phases facing each other across the slot. The amplitude is modulated with a period of $0.5 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 2.4: Amplitude of the electric field obtained from the finite element method solver. Shown is a crosscut through the waveguide. The width w of the waveguide is 40 nm . The field is localized to the air gap. The electric field lines point across the gap, as indicated by dashed black arrows.

Figure 2.5: Results of the finite-difference time-domain simulation for a slot $17 \mu\text{m}$ long. Amplitude of the perpendicular (a) and parallel (b) component of the electric field, 10 nm above a slot with a width of 40 nm . The excitation spot has a Gaussian profile, with a waist of $10 \mu\text{m}$. The simulated fields show agreement with the measurements of figure 2.3(a) and 2.5(a).

2.3 Discussion

To clarify the results further, a finite element method (FEM) solver (COM-SOL) is employed to find the allowed modes of the structure. At widths smaller than ~ 200 nm only one physical solution is found, which has most of the electric field confined to the slot. This is different from the critical slot width of ~ 1 μm found by Pile and co-workers [68], because the gold film in our case is much thinner than the 400 nm used in that work. With the calculation, we also verify the measured symmetry. The electric field resulting from the FEM simulation for a 40 nm wide waveguide is shown in figure 2.4. The measured lateral extent of the mode (~ 600 nm full width at half maximum, FWHM) is larger than the calculated one (150 nm FWHM), which we attribute to the finite size of our near-field probe. The electric field is confined to a lateral size ~ 10 times smaller than the free-space wavelength. The symmetry of the mode is such that electric field lines point in the direction shown by the dashed black arrows in figure 2.4.

The match in the calculated and measured modal symmetry indicates that we are indeed observing the plasmonic slot mode in the waveguide.

Figure 2.6: Results of the finite-difference time-domain simulation for a slot much longer than the size of the laser spot. Amplitude of the perpendicular (a) and parallel (b) component of the electric field, 10 nm above a slot with a width of 40 nm. The modulation seen for shorter slots is absent, which points to scattering off the short edges of the slot as the excitation mechanism.

However, the FEM calculation only shows allowed solutions to Maxwell's equations for a given geometry, hence it does not provide insight into the excitation mechanism and the origin of the modulation in the amplitude images of figure 2.3(a) and 2.3(b). To understand the situation further, we perform finite-element time-domain (FDTD) simulations with the Lumerical Solutions FDTD software. In the simulation, we fix the width of the slot to 40 nm, and vary the slot length and the width of the laser spot. It is observed that for our experimental situation, a 17 μm long slot and a 10 μm

wide ($1/e$ in field) incident beam, the simulation qualitatively reproduces the measured field patterns (figure 2.5). The top part of the figure, which shows the amplitude of the electric field component perpendicular to the slot, shows a weak modulation with a period of $\sim 1.02 \mu\text{m}$, which is approximately λSPP , the calculated wavelength for this slot width. This is the same period which we experimentally observe for the corresponding field component (figure 2.2(a)). The simulated amplitude of the field component parallel to the slot (figure 2.5(b)) displays two superimposed periods. Besides the periodicity corresponding to λSPP also observed for the perpendicular field direction in figure 2.5(b), now an additional periodicity corresponding to $\lambda\text{SPP}/2$ is present, which can be seen most clearly in the middle of the slot. The contrast of the modulation is found to increase for shorter slots and wider laser spots. For longer slots, the contrast of the beating decreases, until finally, in an infinitely long slot, the beating vanishes, as shown in figure 2.6. We therefore conclude that scattering at the slot ends into the plasmonic mode is the excitation mechanism, even though the amplitude of the incident laser at the slot ends is small. The periodicity corresponding to $\lambda\text{SPP}/2$ in the amplitude pattern is then the result of two counterpropagating modes, each launched by one of the slot ends. Due to the high amplitude of the directly transmitted beam, and the relatively weak amplitude of the plasmonic field, the directly transmitted light influences the pattern observed for both field components. The interference between the directly transmitted beam, which has a nearly constant phase along the length of the slot, with the plasmonic slot mode, results in the modulation of the amplitude with a periodicity corresponding to λSPP . It is now obvious that figure 2.2(a) shows primarily a λSPP modulation of the amplitude because the transmitted light dominates for the electric field component orthogonal to the long slot axis. On the other hand, for the electric field component parallel to the long slot axis, simulations show that the exact area where the periodicity corresponding to λSPP dominates the amplitude over the periodicity corresponding to $\lambda\text{SPP}/2$, as well as the shape of the interference pattern, strongly depend on the position of the center of the beam with respect to the slot ends. This can be understood when we consider that moving the excitation spot closer to or further away from one of the slot ends will change the amplitude and phase relation between the different contributing modes and the transmitted beam. Thus, a slight offset of the incident beam with respect to the center of the waveguide can explain the discrepancies between figure 2.3(a) and figure 2.5(b).

2.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, we have excited a plasmonic mode in a subwavelength slot in a gold film. We observed the electric fields of the mode with phase and polarization sensitivity, showing that the mode is antisymmetric, i.e. opposite charges face each other across the air gap. Due to its high confinement, we expect that this mode can be of great use for 2-dimensional plasmonic interconnects, sensing, and quantum plasmonics. The existence of only one mode in the waveguide results in well-known positions of field maxima and minima, which will have to be considered when using such a slot for sensing or interaction with single emitters. The node of the electric field in the middle of the gap, which directly results from the antisymmetric nature of the mode, will affect any particles inserted into the slot. For further improvement of the device, we foresee the need for controlled coupling to this mode, perhaps similarly to the adiabatic coupling to nanowire waveguides [73]. An alternative would be to couple to this mode from a dielectric slot waveguide with the same symmetry, as was shown recently [74].

Chapter 3: Bending losses in plasmonic nanowire waveguides

Metallic nanowires are a good candidate for sub-micrometer sized plasmonic waveguides. They are readily fabricated on glass substrates and can be efficiently coupled to. The sub-wavelength extent of plasmonic nanowire modes makes the notion of creating complex plasmonic circuits attainable. Losses of waveguides in tight bends will be an important issue for any future plasmonic circuit. We study bending losses of curved plasmonic gold nanowire waveguides for radii of curvature ranging from 1 to 12 μm . We use near-field measurements to separate bending losses from propagation losses. The bending losses scale exponentially with radius of curvature. We find attenuation due to bending losses to be $0.1 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ for a curved waveguide with a width of 70 nm and a radius of curvature of 2 μm . Experimental results are supported by Finite Difference Time Domain simulations. An analytical model developed for dielectric waveguides is used to predict the trend of rising bending losses with decreasing radius of curvature in plasmonic nanowires.

3.1 Introduction

In optical data processing, the integration of discrete photonic components onto a chip has been a key objective. Advances have been made in realizing micrometer-scale components like waveguides, switches, delay lines, and routers in silicon-based materials. As these components are increasingly fabricated in compact areas, bending losses become significant. Studies have examined bending losses in photonic crystal, silicon, and silicon-on-insulator (SOI) waveguides. Recently, subwavelength confinement has been achieved using surface plasmon polariton (SPP) optics, offering an alternative for guiding light on a submicron scale. Metal strips can confine plasmons in two-dimensional waveguides, and further innovations have led to high-confinement SPP waveguides, including triangular wedges, dielectric stripes on metal, slot waveguides, and metallo-dielectric fiber waveguides. Integrated plasmonic components like interferometers, ring resonators, and S-shaped bends have been successfully demonstrated. Metal nanowires also support guided plasmonic modes for extremely small radii, with nanowires as narrow as 60 nm being fabricated on chips and coupled from the far field.

This chapter focuses on bending losses in plasmonic nanowire waveguides. Using an adiabatic coupling method, nanowire plasmon polaritons (NPPs) are excited in wires 70 nm and 40 nm wide, and their propagation is analyzed through bends with radii ranging from 1 to 12 μm . A near-field microscope is employed to measure the electric field in both straight and curved sections of the wires. The transmission through bends is examined as a function of radius of curvature, with propagation losses due to Ohmic damping and surface roughness accounted for by analyzing straight wire segments. The remaining transmission losses are attributed to pure bending loss, and the results are validated through Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD) simulations. An analytical model is used to describe the relationship between bending losses and curvature radius.

3.2 Sample fabrication and near-field measurement

Gold nanowires are fabricated on a BK-7 glass substrate through electron beam lithography. First, a 150 nm thick layer of positive resist (Zep520) is spin-coated onto the substrate, followed by a conductive polymer layer necessary for electron beam exposure. After exposure, the sample is developed in N-amyl acetate, removing the exposed resist. A 50 nm thick gold layer is evaporated onto the substrate, and the remaining resist and gold are lifted off using N-Methyl pyrrolidone. The resulting structures include a grating of subwavelength holes and a taper leading to a curved nanowire waveguide. The grating has a 1 μm pitch, optimized for exciting surface plasmon polaritons (SPPs) at the gold/glass interface, with a free-space wavelength of 1.55 μm . The SPPs propagate into the tapered waveguide and are funneled into a nanowire, with widths of 40 or 70 nm, as confirmed by scanning electron microscope (SEM) images. The nanowire waveguides were designed to make 90° bends, with radii of curvature (RC) ranging from 1 to 12 μm .

To probe the electric field locally, a phase- and polarization-sensitive near-field scanning optical microscope was used, employing an aluminum-coated near-field aperture probe with a diameter of about 300 nm. The microscope measured the near-field electric field amplitude in both straight and curved nanowire configurations. For example, one measurement shows SPPs approaching a curved nanowire with a 6 μm radius of curvature, and propagating along the nanowire without significant light leakage at the bend.

Figure 3.1: Scanning electron micrographs (a and b) and measured near-field amplitudes (c and d) of straight (b and d) and curved (a and c) sections of a 70 nm wide nanowire waveguide. D is an enlargement of a straight section indicated with a white box in c.

3.3 Characterization of losses

3.3.1 Transmission through nanowire bends

Figure 3.2 illustrates the amplitude transmittance through curved nanowires with widths of 40 nm and 70 nm as a function of the radius of curvature (RC). The amplitude transmittance is calculated by comparing the signal strength before and after the curve. The highest transmittance, 0.53, is observed for a waveguide with a 70 nm width and a 2 μm RC. A general trend of decreasing transmittance with increasing RC is evident across all waveguides studied.

For lossy waveguides, the intensity typically drops exponentially along the path. A single exponential decay function is fitted to the last three data points in the graph, represented by a dashed line. Notably, the data point for the smallest RC lies well below the fitted line for both cases, suggesting that an additional loss component influences the results at smaller RCs.

The simplest assumption is that the loss in the bends consists of two components, one for the propagation loss and one for the bending loss. Separating the two components while still keeping the exponential form yields:

$$A_{out}/A_{in} = \exp(-k_{propagation}x) \exp(-k_{bending}x) \quad (3.1)$$

In equation 3.1, $k_{propagation}$ represents the attenuation of the electric field per unit length due to propagation losses, $k_{bending}$ represents the attenuation due to bending losses, and x is the length along the waveguide. A_{out}/A_{in} is the amplitude transmittance around the bend, which can also be expressed as $\exp(-k_{total}x)$, where k_{total} is the total attenuation of the electric field per unit length through the bend.

3.3.2 Propagation losses

In plasmonic structures, propagation losses generally stem from two components: Ohmic and scattering losses. Ohmic losses arise from power dissipation due to electron scattering within the metal, while scattering losses occur when power from the propagating mode is converted into free radiation, caused by imperfections in the surface or bulk of the material. Both of these loss mechanisms are present in both straight and curved nanowire sections, affecting overall performance.

Figure 3.2: Amplitude transmittance through a 90° bend as a function of radius of curvature. Blue and green points correspond to waveguides with widths of 70 nm and 40 nm, respectively. Dashed lines are exponential fits with a single exponent to the last three data points of the near-field amplitude transmittance measurements. The errorbars represent the experimental uncertainty. The insets show near-field amplitude images of two investigated structures.

Comparing the slopes of the fits for the two different waveguide widths in figure 3.2, we observe that the transmission in a 40 nm wide nanowire decreases faster with increasing RC. In contrast to the case of a dielectric waveguide, where the mode is gradually expelled as the guide is narrowed, in the case of nanowire plasmons the mode retracts into the wire as it gets narrower [88, 92, 73]. Consequently, in narrower waveguides a larger fraction of the mode resides in the metal and hence Ohmic losses are higher than in wider wires. By fitting a decaying exponential function to the amplitude in straight nanowire sections, we obtain average values of $k_{\text{propagation}} = 0.2 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ in 40 nm wide waveguides, and $k_{\text{propagation}} = 0.085 \pm 0.006 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ in 70 nm wide waveguides. As expected, the propagation attenuation is smaller in the wider waveguide.

3.3.3 Isolating the bending losses

From equation 3.1 and the presented data, we can extract a value for k_{bending} by substituting x by $RC/2$ (the path traversed in a 90° bend).

This yields

$$k_{\text{bending}}'' = -\log \frac{A_{\text{out}}}{A_{\text{in}}} \frac{2}{\pi RC} - k_{\text{propagation}}'' \quad (3.2)$$

In the above equation, we have made the assumption that propagation losses are the same in straight sections of the waveguide as in the curved sections.

Figure 3.3: Attenuation due to bending losses obtained for waveguides with a width of 70 nm. (a) experimentally obtained values for k_{total} (green), $k_{\text{propagation}}$ (blue) and k_{bending} (orange). (b) Attenuation values obtained from FDTD simulations. The dashed orange lines indicate the fit to an exponential function. The error bars in the left image represents experimental uncertainty. In the right image, the error bars represent the uncertainty in placing power monitors exactly at the beginning and end of a bend.

3.3.4 Simulation

We compared the experimental results with Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD) simulations using Lumerical FDTD Solutions v6.5.11. In the simulations, the substrate was modeled as a uniform BK7 slab with a refractive index of 1.50066. The gold's permittivity was fitted to a Drude model, based on ellipsometry measurements from a similar sample at a wavelength of 1.55 μm . Perfectly matched layers (PML) were applied around the simulation box to absorb radiated power.

The nanowire's cross-section was modeled as a rectangle, 70 nm wide and 50 nm high. A finite difference frequency domain solver was used to calculate the mode profile, serving as the excitation source at the nanowire's intersection with the simulation boundary. The mode exhibited its highest intensity at the surface of the gold wire, producing strong electric field gradients, particularly at the corners. To ensure adequate resolution of the gradient, the mesh size was varied from 10 nm to as fine as 1 nm. No significant change in transmittance was observed when reducing the mesh size from 2 nm to 1 nm. Therefore, the final simulations used a 2 nm mesh for the smallest elements.

To verify that the absorption of the evanescent tail by the PML didn't affect the results, we adjusted the size of the simulation box. A distance of 1.2 μm between the structure and the PML was found sufficient to produce reliable results.

A simple model to describe radiation loss in bends leads to bending losses that depend exponentially on the radius of curvature RC [94]:

$$k''_{bending} = C_1 \exp(-C_2 RC), \text{ where } C_2 = \beta(2\Delta n_{eff}/n_{eff})^{3/2} \quad (3.3)$$

The effective index in plasmonic nanowires with a width of 40 nm is only slightly higher than the index in the underlying glass substrate, whereas the index contrast in dielectric waveguides can be significantly higher [82].

Table 3.1: Coefficients obtained by fitting to equation 3.3

	$C_1[\mu m^{-1}]$	$C_2[\mu m^{-1}]$
Experiment (70 nm)	0.289 ± 0.081	0.461 ± 0.140
FDTD simulation (70 nm)	0.348 ± 0.015	0.752 ± 0.048
Experiment (40 nm)	0.638 ± 0.077	0.457 ± 0.096
FDTD simulation (40 nm)	0.361 ± 0.041	1.040 ± 0.012

Figure 3.4: The fraction of energy in the substrate. BK-7 is the glass substrate; Au is the gold nanowire. X is the distance from the center of the nanowire waveguide. The green and blue dots are results of numerical simulations for wires of width 40 nm and 70 nm, respectively. The shaded area of the substrate marks the area from which the fraction is calculated. An exponentially decaying dependence on X is observed, which is confirmed with overlaid exponential fits (red lines).

Chapter 4: The Talbot effect for surface plasmon polaritons

Subwavelength-sized holes in metal films are frequently used to launch surface plasmon polaritons (SPPs). These holes are easy to fabricate and can create a variety of near- and far-field intensity patterns. In our study, we use a chain of subwavelength holes to launch SPPs on a gold-air interface. With a phase-sensitive near-field microscope, we visualize the electric field of the excited SPPs and observe self-images of the chain, which we attribute to the Talbot effect. Far from the chain, we detect the diffraction orders of the SPPs. When the hole spacing is comparable to the wavelength, we find that revivals do not occur at the standard Talbot distance. Instead, we propose an alternative expression for the Talbot distance that applies to these smaller spacings. We study the behavior of the revivals and diffraction orders, noting that the Talbot revivals become more pronounced as the number of holes increases, consistent with numerical simulations. These findings could be valuable for multiplexing sensor applications, where precise control over local SPP intensity is essential.

References

[1]